

Preparation of a $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_3$ (LSCF) cathode material by gel combustion method for IT-SOFCs : Spectroscopic, electrochemical and microstructural analysis[†]

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Abstract : In this work, the performance of a nanocrystalline LSCF composite as a cathode material was investigated. The cathode LSCF composite was successfully synthesized via gel-combustion route. The synthesized LSCF composite material was characterized for microstructural and electrochemical performance by SEM, XRD, BET, FTIR, TGA-DTA, and impedance spectroscopy. The prepared LSCF material shows the high surface area of 68 m²/g. The XRD analysis reveals the nanocrystalline structure of synthesized material. FTIR spectra confirm the formation of mixed metal oxide at high temperature. TGA/DTA analysis reveals that the synthesized LSCF composite is highly stable at high temperatures. The impedance measurement suggested that as-synthesized LSCF composite material can be used as cathode in the fabrication of IT-SOFCs.

Keywords : Cathode, fuel cells, impedance, SOFCs, TGA-DTA.

Introduction

Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) based on intermediate temperature has gained considerable interest in recent years due to its potential in generation of electrical energy with ecofriendly approach. SOFCs possess several advantage such as high efficiency, multi-fuel capability and co-generation over the other fuel cells and are commonly operated at high temperature (800–1000 °C)¹. However, the operation of SOFCs at high temperature causes physicochemical degradation of SOFCs cell materials². Meanwhile, there has been continuous considerable research to lower down the operating temperature at an intermediate level ~600–900 °C³. As a result, intermediate temperature SOFCs requires not only new anode, cathode, and electrolyte materials but also sophisticated microstructure and electrochemical development of the cathode. Lanthanum Strontium Manganite (LSM) is widely used as a cathode material in SOFCs because of its excellent mechanical, thermal and physicochemical stability at high temperature⁴. Hence, cathode materials with higher conductivity than LSM in the intermediate temperature range

should be used in order to decrease the resistance as well as cell operating temperature⁵. Lanthanum Strontium Cobalt Ferrite (LSCF) based materials are considered to be suitable candidates for intermediate temperature application because of their high physicochemical, thermal and mechanical properties⁶.

In the present study, we synthesized a $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_3$ (LSCF) material with high conductivity using gel-combustion method. The synthesized LSCF powder was characterized for microstructural and electrochemical performance by SEM, XRD, BET, FTIR, TGA-DTA and impedance spectroscopy.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 reveals that the morphology of the nano-material was smooth and somewhat spherical in shape, and the particle was found to be in the nano size range. The XRD results showed the presence of crystalline particles and the obtained peaks were in good agreement with rhombohedral perovskite structure of LSCF powder (Fig. 2). The average crystallite size was also evaluated by Debye-

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

Fig. 1. SEM micrograph of the synthesized LSCF composites.

Fig. 2. XRD spectra of the synthesized LSCF composites calcined at 400, 700 and 900 °C.

Scherrer's formula⁷. The average crystallite size calculated for calcined LSCF material at 400, 700 and 900 °C were 58, 36 and 27 nm, respectively. The BET surface area was measured by nitrogen adsorption-desorption and was 68 m²/g for calcined LSCF material at 900 °C, whereas the BJH desorption pore size distribution was 18.32–8.57 m²/g, the total pore volume was 0.2365 cc/g and the average BET pore size was 260.46 Å.

Fig. 3 reveals the FTIR spectra of the as-prepared LSCF composite material. A broad and intense absorption band appeared in the as-prepared sample at around 3500 cm⁻¹ which was due to the presence of adsorbed water or OH stretching group in alcohol. However, the stretching of OH group disappeared with increase of temperature from 150 to 900 °C which further indicates about the loss of adsorbed water from the sample at higher temperature. The presence of peak at 1480 cm⁻¹ is attributed

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of the as-prepared LSCF composite materials.

to C–H bending while symmetric C=O band appears at 1423 cm⁻¹⁸. These peaks become less intense with the increase in temperature. The small band appearing between 800 to 500 cm⁻¹ was mainly due to the metal oxide interaction⁹.

The TGA/DTA curve of prepared LSCF material by gel combustion process is given in Fig. 4. The major weight loss occurred in three steps. At the initial stage about 5% weight loss was found between 200–400 °C which was due to the presence of adsorbed moisture in sample. In the second step, weight loss of about 8% was observed between 500–700 °C, which was also accompanied by the endothermic peaks at 300 and 750 °C in the DTA curve which reveals the decomposition of oxide precursors to form perovskite oxide. After that, about 6% weight loss occurred at 800 °C. Fig. 4 reveals the formation of perovskite oxide starts at 500 °C and completes at 800 °C and beyond that insignificant weight loss was observed.

Fig. 5(a) demonstrates impedance spectra measured for as-synthesized typical cathode sample at three different temperatures. The impedance profile obtained for the LSCF sample particularly at 400 and 700 °C clearly reveals presence of two arcs like structure. The first arc situated at the left side on the impedance real axis corresponds to resistance offered by the grain boundary of the LSCF sample while second arc positioned at right side indicated resistance offered by bulk boundary¹⁰. The intercept obtained at the right side on the impedance (real) axis at low frequency represents the total resistance (R_T)

Fig. 4. TGA/DTA pattern of LSCF composite prepared by gel combustion process.

Fig. 5. Impedance spectra of synthesized LSCF composite at different temperatures (a) and Arrhenius plot (b).

and the intercept at left side on the same axis at higher frequency represents the ohmic resistance (R_0)¹¹. The polarization resistance (R_p) can be evaluated by subtracting the total resistance (R_t) from ohmic resistance (R_0). The polarization resistance (R_p) calculated for LSCF samples at 400, 700 and 900 °C were 0.31 Ω cm², 0.22 Ω cm² and 0.11 Ω cm². The low values of polarization resistance obtained for LSCF samples attributed to fast oxygen

ion diffusivity in the bulk¹². The activation energy (E_a) of the cathode sample was also calculated from the Arrhenius plot given in Fig. 5(b). The E_a calculated from the slope of the linearly fitted line as $E_a = 62.2$ kJ/mol, representing the low activity energy for oxygen dissociation and adsorption¹³.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents :

All of the reagents were of analytical grade with the mass fraction purity of 0.99 and used as received without further purification. $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were purchased from Thomas Baker, Mumbai, India. $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, glycine ($\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$), NaOH and HNO_3 were purchased from E. Merck, Mumbai, India, and $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was purchased from Alfa Aesar, England.

Synthesis of LSCF :

The required amount of $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were first dissolved and mixed in 100 mL of distilled water by magnetic stirring at room temperature. After complete dissolution of the metal nitrates, glycine, which is a metal ions binding agent and acts as a fuel in combus-

tion reaction added to the mixed metal solution. The molar ratio of glycine and metal nitrate oxidants was set to 1. The transparent aqueous solution holding the metal nitrates and glycine was then heated on a hot plate under magnetic stirring. It was converted to a viscous gel and ignited to flame at 150 °C. After the auto-ignition of mixed metal oxidants with glycine, the obtained material was heated at 80 °C for 10 h followed by calcinations at different temperature of 400, 700 and 900 °C for 3 h to give black colored LSCF powder.

Characterization :

The surface morphology of LSCF was studied using scanning electron microscopy (FEI Quanta 200 MK2, Japan) at an electron accelerated voltage of 20 kV. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was conducted using a Philips X'pert Pro diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54060 \text{ \AA}$). FTIR spectra of the LSCF nanocomposites was collected with a FTLA-2000 ABB spectrophotometer, Canada in the range $400\text{--}4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, using a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 32 scans to determine the surface functional groups. The spectra of the dried samples were obtained in KBr pellets (Merck, spectroscopic grade) containing 1 wt% of LSCF nanocomposites. The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area was measured by a N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherm at temperature 77 K using an Autoasorb 1C instrument for BET. The BET and Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) methods were used to calculate the surface area of synthesized LSCF nanocomposites. The thermal stability was studied by thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA), under a dynamic air atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 min^{-1} using a Perkin-Elmer TGA instrument. Impedance spectra were measured by means of Solartron machine, performed at a temperature of $400\text{--}900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with temperature intervals of $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Conclusions

An advanced LSCF composite material was successfully synthesized by gel-combustion route. The synthesized LSCF material shows the high surface area ($68 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) which is beneficial for fabrication of cathode material in intermediate temperature SOFCs. The average crystallite size for calcined LSCF material was found to be 58,

36 and 27 nm at 400, 700 and 900 °C, which reveals that the prepared composite material is in the range of nanoscale. TGA/DTA analysis reveals that the synthesized LSCF composite is highly stable at high temperatures. The impedance measurement suggested that as-synthesized LSCF cathode powder shows reasonably high impedance value of $0.11 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ at 900 °C. Therefore, the study recommended that as-synthesized LSCF material can be used for the fabrication of cathode materials in IT-SOFCs.

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